

IDENTIFYING AMINO ACIDS THAT REGULATE SHUTTLING BETWEEN THE
NUCLEUS AND CYTOPLASM IN AN RNA-BINDING DOMAIN OF THE PTBP1 PROTEIN

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ABSTRACT

RNA alternative splicing of gene exons is an essential process found in all eukaryotes. It contributes to functional and phenotypic diversity, such as hormone production and muscle formation, depending on exon patterns originating from a single gene. This mechanism efficiently promotes organismal complexity given a minimal genome. PTBP1 is an important regulator in this process; mutated PTBP1 is associated with cancer and neurodegenerative conditions. PTBP1 transport between the nucleus and cytoplasm is controlled by sequences within the protein itself, including classic import and export sequences (NLS and NES, respectively), and one of PTBP1's four RNA Recognition Motifs, RRM2. However, which amino acids in RRM2 regulate transport remain unknown. Five sequences similar to known NES motifs were identified in RRM2 (NES 1-5) and individually deleted from PTBP1 to gauge their effect on export. Mutant proteins were expressed in human osteosarcoma cells and expression was visualized via fluorescence microscopy. Two mutants (NES 2, 4) were primarily nuclear and will now undergo a specific nuclear export assay. Three mutants (NES 1, 3, 5) did not show a consistent trend and are undergoing additional trials. The controls were located as expected. Given the conservation of PTBP1 from insects to humans, understanding its nuclear export regulation provides greater insight into this multifunctional protein.

Keywords: PTBP1, RRM2, shuttling, nuclear export, splicing

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A. INTRODUCTION

The human genome is made up of DNA that encodes the biological information needed to construct and sustain life. RNA binding proteins have sparked much interest given their ability to regulate gene maturation mechanisms such as alternative splicing (Chaudhury et al., 2010, p. 1450). RNA alternative splicing of gene exons is an essential process found amongst all eukaryotes. It contributes to functional and phenotypic diversity, such as hormone production and muscle formation, depending on the exon patterns originating from that of a single gene. This mechanism efficiently promotes organismal complexity given a minimal genome.

B. BACKGROUND

STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION OF PTBP1

Polypyrimidine tract binding protein 1 (PTBP1) is an important regulator in this process. However, when mutated, PTBP1 is associated with the progression of various cancers and neurodegenerative conditions (Zhu et al., 2020, p. 122). PTBP1 contains four RNA Recognition Motifs, RRM 1-4, which help facilitate protein interactions and binding affinities to pyrimidine-rich sequences (Pérez et al., 1977, p. 11881). As shown in Figure 1, the N-terminal 60 amino acid residues of PTBP1 houses its independent (autonomous) nuclear localization and export signals, NLS and NES, respectively (reviewed in Li and Yen, 2002, p. 10310). These signals enable the PTB protein to travel (shuttle) between the nuclear and cytoplasmic regions of a cell with respect to its designated function.

Figure 1. PTBP1 Schematic Representation and Sequence Diagram

(A) A schematic representation of the PTB protein indicating each distinctive region — N-terminus, RNA Recognition Motifs (RRM), and Linkers. (B) A sequence diagram of the five putative NES sequences. Autonomous nuclear localization signal (NLS) and nuclear export signal (NES) of PTBP1 are located within the first 60 amino acid residues of the N-terminal region. Red arrowheads are lysines that are acetylated. Black vertical lines are amino acids that interact with RNA.

PTBP1 is involved in regulating alternative splicing within the nucleus of a cell as well as RNA localization and translation in the cytoplasm. Keppetipola et al. (2012) illustrates that the RRM of PTB have unique roles in terms of alternative splicing (p. 11). RRM2, in specific, has

been known to be a major player between protein to protein interactions and is required for its shuttling ability while RRM3 and RRM4 are important for RNA binding (Kamath et al., 2001, p. 3808).

Figure 2. Diagram of Alternative Splicing (Zhu, 2020)

A schematic representation of alternative splicing of the PTBP1 protein. Green oval indicates unspliced protein (TOP). Blue Rectangles represent coding regions (exons) while the black lines represent the non-coding regions (introns) of the premature mRNA transcript (MIDDLE). As shown by the dotted lines, the removal of introns via spliceosomes enable for various exon patterns to originate from PTBP1 when forming the mature mRNA transcript (BOTTOM).

NUCLEAR LOCALIZATION AND EXPORT

PTBP1 belongs to a family of key proteins that regulate cellular nucleic acid metabolism known as heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoproteins (hnRNPs). The functional properties of

these proteins differ depending on where they are localized within a cell (Geuens et al., 2016, p. 852). Previous studies indicate that PTBP1 possesses autonomous nuclear localization and export signals that promote protein shuttling (Han et al., 2010, p. 380).

In the classic nuclear import pathway, importin α promotes the initial interaction between a cargo protein containing a NLS and importin β 1 receptor; the release of the cargo protein into the nucleus is mediated by Ran-GTP in the nuclear pore complex (Kosugi et al., 2009, 2053). In turn, the cargo protein appears predominantly present within the nucleus of a cell. In the case of PTBP1, all N-terminal 60 amino acid residues are essential for functional NLS activity (Li and Yen, 2002, p. 10306).

In the classic nuclear export pathway, CRM1 interacts with Ran-GTP in the nuclear pore complex; the release of the cargo protein into the cytoplasm is mediated by the hydrolysis of Ran-GTP to Ran-GDP (Kosugi et al., 2009, 2053). In turn, the cargo protein appears predominantly present within the cytoplasm of a cell. In the case of PTBP1, the first 25 residues function as its autonomous NES with residues 11-16 being crucial for its overall nuclear export activity.

RRM2 regulates the ability of PTB to travel (shuttle) between the nucleus and cytoplasm of a cell; it is hypothesized to contain additional NES sequences apart from its autonomous NES and NLS; thereby, facilitating a key role in its nuclear export activity (Kamath et al., 2001, p. 3817). However, the specific amino acids sequences that enable this function to occur still remain unknown.

C. PROBLEM STATEMENT & RESEARCH QUESTION(S)

The main focus of my research project aims to determine whether single deletion mutations to amino acid sequences found within RRM2 of PTBP1 influence the shuttling of the protein between the nucleus and cytoplasmic region of a cell. Thus, the question arises: Do deletions of amino acid sequences similar to known nuclear export signal (NES) motifs affect the subcellular localization of PTBP1?

D. RESEARCH AIMS & OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of this research project is to gain insight on the subcellular localization of PTBP1 by way of fluorescence microscopy using human osteosarcoma (MG63) cells that have been transfected with plasmids containing singular deletion mutations in one of its four RNA recognition motifs (RRM2). It is hypothesized that these modifications may alter its nucleocytoplasmic shuttling abilities. However, it is also possible that these modifications may have no effect on nuclear export activity. Since PTPB1 has been associated with various pathologies, identifying where it is localized in a cell may contribute to the development of therapeutic advancements in medical research. This leads to the overall big picture of my study which enables us to gain a better understanding of how life works.

E. METHODOLOGY

CELL CULTURE AND TRANSFECTION

MG63 cells were grown and maintained in a media stock composed of 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and Dulbeccos' Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) at 37 °C. This solution and temperature provides a suitable nutrient-rich environment for the attachment, growth, and

proliferation of healthy mammalian cells. The viability and confluency of the cultured cells were monitored. Cells were split on a weekly basis to avoid overcrowding of the petri dish. To do this, the media stock was removed (aspirated) and the cells were washed using Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS). Upon aspirating the PBS, the adhered cells were promoted to detach from the petri dish using Trypsin and incubated at 37 °C for 3-5 minutes. The detached cells were then mixed/resuspended (triturated) with 10% FBS, DMEM solution to break up any clumps/clusters. From there, the triturated cells were then added onto a new petri dish containing the 10% FBS, DMEM solution. Note that the volume used may differ depending on the determined split ratio.

Using a 24-well plate, individual coverslips were added onto their respective wells and submerged (treated) in a 0.2% Gelatin solution for 30 minutes at 37 °C to enable proper adhesion of the cells onto the glass surface. Upon incubation, the Gelatin solution was aspirated and coverslips were washed with PBS. Cells were trypsinized like mentioned above in preparation for plating. 20 µL of the cell solution was pipetted into a microcentrifuge tube and stained with 10 µL of Trypan Blue; a hemocytometer was used to calculate the amount of cells needed per well. Using the calculated value, a working stock of the remaining trypsinized cells and 10% FBS, DMEM media was made; 0.6 mL of this solution was distributed into each well.

After a 24 hour incubation period in 37 °C, each well was examined for cell confluency. If cells were approximately 100% confluent at the center of the coverslip, cells were transfected with its respective plasmid aliquot containing 500 ng/uL of DNA , 25µL of Optimem, and 0.8 µL of Avalanche. A total of eight different plasmid constructs were used. The controls being wild-type PTBP1 (WT), a loss of NES mutant (S16A), and loss of NLS mutant (K45A). Five sequences similar to known NES motifs were identified in RRM2 (NES 1-5) and individually deleted from the PTBP1 sequence to gauge their effect on export. All PTBP1 genes were

modified with a FLAG tag to differentiate the protein expressed by the plasmids from pre-existing (endogenous) PTBP1 found in the cells.

Figure 3. Schematic of the PTBP1 Plasmid Constructs

A schematic representation of the WT PTB protein indicating each distinctive region —FLAG tag, autonomous NES and NLS, and RNA Recognition Motifs (RRM). S16A serves as the loss of NES control while K45A serves as the loss of NLS control. Mutants NES 1-5 are sequences similar to known NES motifs that were identified within RRM2 (red box) and individually deleted from the PTB to gauge their effect on nuclear export.

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Upon 24 hours of transfection, the cells underwent immunocytochemistry techniques (ICC) at room temperature. For this process, the cells are fixed with 4% PFA in PBS with dissolved Sucrose for 10 minutes and permeabilized with 0.1% TritonX-100 for 5 minutes. A humidified chamber consisting of a well plate lid, Whatman paper soaked in diH₂O, parafilm, and ICC lid was constructed. Coverslips were placed cell-side down in 50 μL of the following solutions: 3% BSA in TBS for 30 minutes, primary antibody (FLAG, 3% BSA in TBS) for 1

hour, and secondary antibody (Alexa-Fluor 488 Donkey α Mouse, DAPI, 3% BSA in TBS for 1 hour. Coverslips were washed with PBS between each step. Upon completion of ICC, the cells were mounted onto glass slides using Prolong Gold and clear nail polish; slides were then stored in a -20 °C freezer.

Expression of PTBP1 was visualized using fluorescence microscopy. Images were captured using the QCapturePro software under its respective wavelengths at 40x objective lens. Adobe Photoshop was then used to adjust light exposure levels and generate the overlay images.

F. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MG63 cells were chosen for this project since: (1) they serve as a great vehicle for transfection given its relatively high level of plasmid absorption and cell adherence and (2) have a well defined, egg-shape-like morphology. In order to determine the localization of PTBP1 within the cells, we devised three distinct categories: primarily nuclear, primarily cytoplasmic, or both.

Figure 4. Criteria for the Subcellular Categorization of PTBP1

To help aid in visualization, I came up with an analogy that matches its egg-shape-like morphology. If we consider a cell to be primarily nuclear, a bright green signal will be seen in

the nuclear region of the cell (aka egg yolk). If we consider a cell to be primarily cytoplasmic, a bright green signal will be seen in the cytoplasmic region of the cell with a dark, hollow region where the nucleus should be located (aka egg white). If we consider a cell to be primary both, a bright green signal can be seen in both nuclear and cytoplasmic regions (aka sunny side up egg).

As shown in Figure 5, it is hypothesized that both WT PTBP1 and S16A will be primarily localized in the nucleus while K45A will appear primarily cytoplasmic. As for the mutants, the effect of the deletion mutation may or may not affect the subcellular location of PTBP1.

Figure 5. Subcellular localization of PTBP1 Controls

A diagram of the predicted subcellular localization of the PTBP1 protein with respect to the plasmid construct used. The loss of NES mutant (K45A) is predicted to be primarily localized in the cytoplasm while both WT and loss of NLS mutant (S16A) is predicted to be primarily nuclear.

Using the methodology shown in Diagram 6, four independent trials were performed. Tentative subcellular localization of PTBP1 was done qualitatively based on the initial skim of the coverslip under the fluorescent microscope. However, in order to quantitatively determine the

relative percentage of PTBP1 found in the nucleus, cytoplasmic, or both regions — 30 cells were counted per coverslip by two independent counters.

Figure 6. Experimental Design Overview

A schematic of the experimental design used to carry out the experimental trials. For more detail, reference the methodology section of the research paper.

The controls were located as predicted: wild-type PTBP1 and S16A were primarily nuclear (75% and 85%, respectively) and K45A was primarily cytoplasmic (57%).

Figure 7. Analysis of the Subcellular Location of PTBP1

Data from the two counters were combined and averaged across all trials; standard deviation was used to generate the range of error bars with respect to its subcellular localization (GRAPH). Trends were calculated using trials that expressed strong fluorescent signals; trials that with poor/no transfection were omitted when generating the percentages (TABLE). If there was discrepancy between counters, those trends would be identified as half of a trial (0.5) instead of a whole trial (1) when taking PTBP1 localization into account.

As shown in Figure 8, NES 2 and NES 4 mutants showed a consistent trend and appeared primarily nuclear (68% and 60%, respectively), suggesting that PTBP1 may have been prevented from nuclear export because these sequences were deleted. Alternatively, given that the mutant plasmids behave like the wild-type, a new hypothesis arises such that the deleted amino acids could have no effect on nuclear export. To address this hypothesis, a more specific nuclear export assay is currently underway. A heterokaryon assay will be performed to differentiate the behavior of these mutants from that of WT PTBP1. In this assay, MG63 cells are fused with another cell line to generate one big cell containing two or more nuclei. If PTB expressed in the nuclei of MG63 cells are exported into the cytoplasm and imported into the nuclei of the other cell type, then this suggests that the deleted sequences are involved in nuclear export activity.

Figure 7. Subcellular localization of Mutants

Both NES 2 (A) and NES 4 (B) mutants express a preliminary nuclear signal suggesting that the deleted sequences may play a role in nuclear export activity.

The other three NES mutants (NES 1, 3, 5) did not show a consistent trend and are currently undergoing additional trials. Subsequently, a swap from fluorescent microscopy to confocal microscopy would yield a better gauge of the subcellular location of our protein of interest.

H. CONCLUSION

Given the conservation of PTBP1 amongst species ranging from insects to humans; theoretically, if we are able to determine the exact amino acid sequences that enable for PTBP1 transport to occur, we could: 1) gain more insight into the regulation of this multifunctional protein and 2) potentially target those specific sequences to either enhance or inhibit the export/import of PTBP1 on a case-by-case basis depending on the positive or negative nature of the spliced proteins. In essence we could prevent pathological cascades from occurring and restore balance within the body.

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